

FATIGUE BEHAVIOUR OF PRE-DAMAGED WELDED STEEL COMPONENTS REINFORCED WITH STEEL PLATES

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Abstract. *Welded steel components subjected to cyclic loading like bridges or crane runway girders are prone to fatigue and therefore, a verification against fatigue failure has to be carried out. This results in a calculated service life according to the applied design code. After expiry of the service life the component is in a normatively unregulated phase of use. A decommissioning would not be economical, if no fatigue cracks occurred. To enable a safe continuing operation the University of Applied Sciences in Munich conducted experimental investigations on different strengthening techniques like HFMI, grinding or reinforcement plates applied on pre-damaged components. In this paper, the fatigue behaviour of pre-damaged components strengthened with steel plates is presented. Different methods of attachments like fitting bolts, high-strength friction grip bolts, self-tapping screws, adhesives and lockbolts were used to attach the steel cover plates. Strain gauge measurements were performed to quantify the reduction of stresses in the vicinity of the strengthened weld detail. Fatigue tests were conducted on specimens that were strengthened at different stages of pre-damage.*

1 REINFORCEMENT WITH STEEL PLATES

1.1 Introduction

Reinforcement plates are used in steel structures to locally strengthen the bearing element e.g. a girder by increasing the cross-sectional area resulting in lower stresses and reduced displacement due to the increased flexural rigidity. Steel sheets are mostly used due to their easy applicability. Practical applications are utility vehicles or steel bridges, for example, see Figure 1. This strengthening method can be used to increase the static load-bearing capacity or to increase the fatigue resistance by reducing the damaging stress range resulting from cyclic loads.

Figure 1: Practical applications for steel reinforcement plates – a) utility vehicles, b) bridges

1.2 Typical methods of attachment

There are numerous methods of attachment for steel reinforcement plates which differ in load transfer, complexity of application and fatigue strength. Three typical methods of attachment are welding, high-strength friction grip bolts (HSFG bolts) and fitting bolts, see Figure 2 and Table 1. To evaluate the fatigue strength the corresponding detail category from EC3-1-9 [1] is used. It is shown that the welded reinforcement plate has a very low fatigue strength, that can be increased by optimizing the plate shape and the weld seam design e.g. run-out weld seams, see [2]. It has to be noted that in case of reinforcement with fitting bolts the nominal stress range has to be calculated using the net gross section of the non-reinforced flange. Therefore, the bolts should be located in an area subjected to small stress ranges. HSFG bolts in comparison are less critical. The load transfer of weld seams and HSFG bolts is nearly lossless. With fitting bolts, a slightly reduced force transfer must be expected due to possible slippage. For all connections the complexity of application is high. HSFG bolts require a complex surface preparation because the contact surfaces must have a sufficient roughness for slip resistance. Fitting bolts require a complex manufacturing of drill holes due to tight tolerances. The welded connection requires positional welding increasing the complexity. To evaluate different methods of attachment the typical methods and additionally self-tapping screws, adhesives and lockbolts were investigated in the course of the research project “NE-Industriebau”[3].

Figure 2: Typical methods of attachment for steel reinforcement plates – a) welding, b) HSFG bolts/fitting bolts

Table 1: Overview – Typical methods of attachment for steel reinforcement plates

method of attachment	load transfer	complexity of application	fatigue strength acc. EC3-1-9 [N/mm ²]
HSFG- bolt	nearly lossless	high (surface preparation)	90 (gross cross-section)
fitting bolt	slight slip	high (tight tolerances)	80 (net cross-section)
welding	nearly lossless	high (positional welding)	36 – 56 (depending on plate thickness)

1.3 Reinforcing pre-damaged components with steel plates

Steel reinforcement plates are frequently used in the retrofit of existing bridges, see [4]. In 55 of the 70 cases of bridge retrofits presented, bolted splices were used to reinforce welded connections. Even cracked components were reinforced with steel plates, often in combination with stop holes or repair welds. Cracked specimens with lateral attachments were reinforced with stop holes, bolted stop holes and stop holes in combination with a bolted splice, see Figure 3. The bolted splice showed the greatest effectiveness increasing the fatigue strength from class F (65 N/mm² at 2x10⁶ load cycles) acc. JNR (Specification for Japanese Railway Bridges [5]) to class C (125 N/mm² at 2x10⁶ load cycles). In [6] and [7] girders with pre-cracked welded cover plate ends were retrofitted using splices with HSFG bolts. The mean fatigue life of the retrofitted components exceeded the AASHTO (American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials) Category B while the non-reinforced detail category is Category E. In [8] bolted reinforcements of cracked welded joints in orthotropic steel bridge decks are presented that show a great efficacy in extending the fatigue life. In order to enlarge the database of fatigue tests on pre-damaged components, that are reinforced with steel plates, multiple methods of attachment were investigated in the course of the research project “NE-Industriebau” [3].

Figure 3: Investigated reinforcement methods [4] – a) drilled stop hole, b) stop hole with HSFG-bolt, c) stop hole with bolted splice (HSFG-bolt)

2. RESEARCH PROJECT “NE-INDUSTRIEBAU”

2.1 Test programme and specimens

In the course of the research project “NE-Industriebau” [3], the University of Applied Sciences Munich conducted fatigue tests on specimens with lateral attachments, see Figure 4. The attachments were welded to the flat steel specimens made of S355 using the MAG-process. The welding parameters are summarized in Table 2. The fatigue tests were performed in a high-frequency resonance pulsator ($R = 0.1$). The abort criterion was defined as a frequency deviation of $\Delta f = -0.1$ for non-reinforced specimens and $\Delta f = -0.2$ for reinforced specimens due to slippage. Tests that exceeded 5x10⁶ load cycles were aborted and declared as run-outs.

Table 2: Welding parameters

Welding process acc. EN ISO 4063	Filler material acc. EN ISO 14341-A	Ø wire [mm]	Shield gas acc. ISO 14175	Current [A]	Voltage [V]	v [mm/s]
135	G 46 4 M21 4Si1	1,0	M21	169-171	26,8	6,7

Figure 4: Specimen with lateral attachments

In the first test series (series A) specimens in as-welded condition were tested without reinforcement plates to determine the characteristic fatigue strength of the welded detail. A fixed slope of $m = 3$ was used to calculate $\Delta\sigma_{C,50\%}$ with a survival probability of 50%. In order to calculate the characteristic fatigue strength $\Delta\sigma_{C,95\%}$ with a survival probability of 95%, a prediction interval acc. [9] was used. In the second test series (series B) the specimens were strengthened in the as-welded state using different methods of attachment and subsequently tested to the abort criterion. The reinforcement plates (flat steel 100x6 with a length of 400 mm) were attached to the top and bottom side of the specimen to prevent an eccentric load transfer. In series C, the specimens were pre-cycled to a damage sum of $D = 1.0$, subsequently checked for cracks with dye penetrant testing, reinforced with steel plates and tested. The number of load cycles to pre-damage the specimens is $N_{D=1,95\%}$ and is calculated using $\Delta\sigma_{C,95\%}$ from series A, see equation 1. Strain gauges were applied at the height of the center of gravity of the base plate with a distance of 20 mm to the lateral attachment to determine the load transfer from base plate to the reinforcement plates. The test programme is summarized in Table 3. The strengthened specimens are shown in Figure 5.

$$N_{D=1,95\%} = \left(\frac{\Delta\sigma_{C,95\%}}{\Delta\sigma} \right)^3 * 2 * 10^6 \quad (1)$$

Table 3: Test programme

Series	Acronym	Method of attachment	Pre-damage D [-]	Number of specimens
A	-	-	0	8
B	aw	welding	0	3
	HFMI	welding + HFMI		3
	FB-M12	fitting bolts M12		3
	FB-M20	fitting bolts M20		3
	HV-M12	HSFG bolts M12		3
	STS	self-tapping screws		3
	LB	lock bolts M12		3
	2K	2-component adhesive	1	
C	STS	self-tapping screw	1,0	3
	LB	lock bolt		3

Series B-aw/HFMI

For series B-aw, the reinforcement plates were welded to the base plate with a circumferential fillet weld. For the test series B-HFMI, the weld toe of the weld seams on the front side were treated with high-frequency mechanical impact treatment (HFMI).

Figure 5: a) Strengthened specimens, b) exemplary hole pattern for bolted/screwed attachments

Series B-FB-M12/M20

For the series with fitting bolts the contact surfaces of the specimen and reinforcement plates were polished using a brushing tool equipped with abrasive paper (P120) to reduce the influence of the surface roughness. The bolt holes were pre-drilled and subsequently reamed to the diameter of the bolt shaft. Fitting bolts M12 and M20 acc. to DIN 609 [10] were used. The nuts were tightened with a $M_{A,h}$ torque acc. to DASt-guideline 024 [11].

Series B-HV-M12

For the series with HSFG bolts, the contact surfaces of the specimen and reinforcement plates were treated with a roller brush, see Figure 6, to create a sufficient surface roughness. The mean roughness R_{y5} acc. to ISO 8503-4 [12] was measured with a stylus profilometer MarSurf PS 10 and amounted to $35,8 \mu\text{m}$. HSFG bolts M12-10.9 acc. to EN 14399-4 [13] were used in combination with wedge lock washers NL12SC. The nuts were tightened using the combined tensioning method acc. to EN 1090-2 [14].

Series B-STTS

For the series B-STTS, 13.4x33 mm self-tapping screws acc. to [15] were used. The contact surfaces were treated as for Series B-FB-M12/20. Before installing the screws, the

reinforcement plates were clamped to the base plate with locking pliers. The screws were installed with an impact wrench with 300 Nm.

Figure 6: Treatment of contact surfaces for slip-resistant connections with a roller brush

Series B-LB

For the series B-LB, lockbolts M12 acc. to [16] were used. Lock bolts are fasteners with a torsion-free axial tensioning process. In a first step the tensioning tool pretensions the bolt and subsequently pushes the locking ring onto the grooved bolt shaft causing the locking ring to deform plastically. This results in an inseparable connection with a low scattering of the preload force i.e. $\pm 5\%$ acc. to [17]. The contact surfaces were treated as for series B-HV-M12.

Series B-2K

For the series B-2K, the reinforcement plates were attached to the base plate with a 2-component epoxy resin. The contact surfaces were sandblasted to Sa 3 acc. ISO 8501-1 to [18] and a roughness medium grit acc. to 8503-1 [19]. The surface was then wiped with isopropanol and the plates were attached. The curing time was 2 weeks. Due to the high frequency of the testing machine (ca. 60 Hz), a negative effect on the adhesive could not be excluded. Therefore, only one specimen for a static strain measurement was manufactured.

2.2 Test results

2.2.1 Strain gauge measurements

To quantify the load transfer from base plate to reinforcement plates one specimen of every method of attachment equipped with strain gauges (FLAB-3-11-5LQM-F) was axially loaded with a tensile force of 100 kN. The results of the strain measurements (mean values of 2 strain gauges) are shown in Figure 7. Since the cross-section is doubled because of the reinforcement plates, a halving of the stress of the non-reinforced specimen is expected in case of lossless load transfer. It is shown that the specimens with welded or adhered reinforcement plates have a lossless load transfer or rather a stress reduction over 50% due to the additional cross-section of the weld seam or adhesive layer. With a 39-41% reduction of stress, the preloaded lockbolts and the self-tapping screws have a slight loss in load transfer. The results of the specimens with fitting bolts show a stress reduction of 30-34% due to slip. It should be noted that due to the distance of the strain gauges to the lateral attachment the measured stresses include a structural stress effect and exceed the expected nominal stress.

Figure 7: Results of strain gauge measurement and position of the strain gauges

2.2.2 Fatigue tests

For details of the fatigue test procedure see chapter 2.1. An overview of the different test series is given in Table 3.

Series A – non-reinforced and as-welded condition

To determine the characteristic fatigue strength of the non-reinforced specimens in as-welded condition, 8 fatigue tests were carried out. All fatigue cracks occurred at the weld toe. The cracks were detected with a mean length of 7 mm. The characteristic fatigue strength amounts to $\Delta\sigma_{C,50\%} = 57.7 \text{ N/mm}^2$ (50% survival probability) or $\Delta\sigma_{C,95\%} = 46.4 \text{ N/mm}^2$ (95% survival probability). The results are shown in Figure 8.

Series B – reinforced and as-welded condition

For series B, fatigue tests on reinforced specimens in as-welded condition were carried out. The results are shown in Table 4 and Figure 8. $N_{50\%,aw}$ describes the number of load cycles that are expected for a non-reinforced lateral attachment in as-welded condition (series A). The mean value of the fatigue life extension that is achieved by the reinforcement is $\mu(N/N_{50\%,aw})$. Due to the doubling of the cross-section the nominal stress range is halved. With a fixed slope of $m = 3$, this results in an expectable life extension factor of 8.

For the specimens with welded reinforcement plates, the fatigue cracks occurred at the weld root (series B-aw/HFMI). For the series with non-preloaded fasteners (series B-FB-M12/M20, series B-STs), the fatigue cracks occurred at the weld toe of the lateral attachment or in the net cross-section of the base plate. For all specimens with preloaded fasteners, the fatigue cracks occurred at the weld toe of the lateral attachment.

The welded reinforcement plate without HFMI treatment (series B-aw) does not significantly extend the fatigue life. The welded and HFMI-treated plates (series B-HFMI) as well as the non-preloaded fasteners show a mean fatigue life extension of 6.8 – 8.8. This life extension matches the expectable extension factor. The attachment with preloaded fasteners results in a mean fatigue life extension of 13.5 - 14.8 exceeding the expectable extension factor. Compressive residual stresses resulting from the preloading process possibly contribute to the fatigue life extension.

Table 4: Results of fatigue tests - series B

Series	Nr.	$\Delta\sigma$ [N/mm ²]	N	N _{50%,aw}	$\frac{N}{N_{50\%,aw}}$ [-]	$\mu\left(\frac{N}{N_{50\%,aw}}\right)$ [-]
B-aw	1	150	218,978	113,837	1.9	1.7
	2	100	680,000	384,200	1.8	
	3	100	500,000	384,200	1.3	
B-HFMI	1	150	639,372	113,837	5.6	8.8
	2	100	3,004,816	384,200	7.8	
	3	100	5,000,000	384,200	13.0	
B-FB-M12	1	150	439,041	113,837	3.9	6.9
	2	100	4,569,022	384,200	11.9	
	3	100	1,866,796	384,200	4.9	
B-FB-M20	1	150	406,604	113,837	3.6	6.8
	2	100	1,413,087	384,200	3.7	
	3	100	5,000,000	384,200	13.0	
B-HV-M12	1	150	1,631,453	113,837	14.3	13.5
	2	100	5,000,000	384,200	13.0	
	3	180	863,022	65,878	13.1	
B-STs	1	150	348,455	113,837	3.1	7.4
	2	100	3,498,497	384,200	9.1	
	3	100	3,828,649	384,200	10.0	
B-LB	1	150	1,724,791	113,837	15.2	14.8
	2	100	5,000,000	384,200	13.0	
	3	180	1,067,000	65,878	16.2	

Figure 8: Results of fatigue tests – series A + B

Series C – reinforced and pre-damaged

For series C, the specimens were pre-damaged with $N_{D=1,95\%}$, see 2.1, checked for cracks with dye penetrant testing, reinforced with plates and tested to the abort criterion. No fatigue cracks were detected during the inspection with dye penetrant testing after the pre-damaging. Self-tapping screws were used as fasteners. The test results are shown in Table 5. ΣN is the sum of pre-damage load cycles $N_{D=1,95\%}$ together with the load cycles that were applied after the reinforcement. The mean value of the fatigue life extension that is achieved by the reinforcement is $\mu(\Sigma N/N_{50\%,aw})$. The results show that the reinforcement with self-tapping screws is also efficient for pre-damaged components.

Table 5: Test results – series C

Series	Nr.	$\Delta\sigma$ [N/mm ²]	pre-damage D [-]	$\Sigma N = N_{D=1,95\%,aw} + N$ [-]	$N_{50\%,aw}$ [-]	$\frac{\Sigma N}{N_{50\%,aw}}$ [-]	$\mu\left(\frac{\Sigma N}{N_{50\%,aw}}\right)$ [-]
	1	150		359,624	113,837	3.2	
C-STS	2	100	1.0	4,027,892	384,200	10.5	8.0
	3	100		3,980,585	384,200	10.4	

3. SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

It could be shown that the reinforcement of pre-damaged components with steel plates was successfully applied in practical applications and multiple research projects. In the course of the research project “NE-Industriebau” [3], 7 different methods of attachment for reinforcement plates were tested on specimens in as-welded condition for load transfer and fatigue. It could be shown that mechanical fasteners and welding in combination with HFMI are suited for the attachment of reinforcement plates subjected to fatigue. Fatigue tests on pre-damaged specimens showed that self-tapping screws are also suited for reinforcement of pre-damaged components.

In the further course of the project, fatigue tests on pre-damaged specimens with lateral attachments and girders with transverse stiffeners will be carried out. As methods of attachment, self-tapping screws and lockbolts will be investigated. Crack propagations measurements on cracked specimens with and without reinforcement plates will be performed to quantify the influence of reinforcement plates on the stress intensity factor depending on the used method of attachment. Based on the experimental and numerical investigations, an inspection-, design- and execution recommendation for reinforcing pre-damaged components will be developed.

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